

Nine new records of spiders (Arachnida: Aranei) from Azerbaijan

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Abstract

This study reports nine spider species newly recorded from Azerbaijan. Six of these – *Lasophorus zografae* Chatzaki, 2018, *Zelotes fulvaster* (Simon, 1878), *Z. prishutovae* Ponomarev & Tsvetkov, 2006, *Hahnia rossii* Brignoli, 1977, *Artema doriae* (Thorell, 1881), and *Synema anaticum* Demir, Aktaş & Topçu, 2009) – are documented for the first time in the Caucasus. The remaining three – *Berlandina nabozhenkoi* Ponomarev & Tsvetkov, 2006, *Bassaniodes robustus* (Hahn, 1832), and *Cetonana laticeps* (Canestrini, 1868) – represent new records for Azerbaijan only. These findings expand the known spider diversity of the Caucasus and increase the total number of species recorded from Azerbaijan to 785. All species are illustrated with photographs.

Keywords

Aranei, fauna, new records, spiders, Caucasus

Introduction

The spider fauna of Azerbaijan currently comprises 776 species (Nuruyeva and Zamani 2025; Nuruyeva et al. 2025). A major contribution to the development of modern knowledge on the country's araneofauna was made by P. Dunin (1989; 1990; 1991; 1992 a, b, c; 1993), who described about 70 species new to science and

documented a large number of taxa. The most intensive progress in arachnological research occurred in the 21st century, particularly during the period 2002–2008, and was associated with a series of systematic and faunistic studies by Huseynov and his co-authors (Logunov and Guseinov 2002; Marusik and Guseinov 2003; Marusik et al. 2003 a, b, 2005 a, b; Guseinov et al. 2005; Logunov and Huseynov 2008). These works significantly expanded knowledge of the taxonomic composition and distribution of spiders in Azerbaijan, including the description of new taxa. Substantial contributions to the study of the Azerbaijani spider fauna have also been made by other arachnologists (Azarkina 2003, 2004; Kovblyuk et al. 2013a, c; Ponomarev et al. 2024). Examination of both existing collection material and specimens collected in 2025, revealed nine species newly recorded from Azerbaijan. The current article presents data on these records, all species are illustrated with photographs.

Materials and methods

Specimens and their copulatory organs were photographed using a Sony DSC-P8 camera mounted on a Nikon SMZ 1270 stereomicroscope. The Caucasus region is defined according to the checklist of Mikhailov (2024), encompassing both the Northern and Southern Caucasus.

Depository: IZBA = Institute of Zoology, Baku, Azerbaijan (N. Snegovaya).

Results

Gnaphosidae Banks, 1892

Berlandina Dalmas, 1922

Berlandina nabozhenkoi Ponomarev & Tsvetkov, 2006

Figure 1

Berlandina nabozhenkoi Ponomarev 2008: 79, f. 1-2 (♂♀); Ponomarev et al. 2018: 246, f. 1-2 (♀); Seropian et al. 2024: 187, f. 1-2 (♀).

For a complete list of six taxonomic entries, see World Spider Catalog (2026).

Material examined. 1 ♀ (IZBA), Azerbaijan: Nakhchivan region: Julfa Distr., under a stone, 26.VI.2012, E.Huseynov.

Distribution. Turkey, Russia (Europe), Iran (World Spider Catalog 2026) and Georgia (Seropian et al. 2024).

Comment. The first record for the fauna of Azerbaijan.

Lasophorus* Chatzaki, 2018**Lasophorus zografae* Chatzaki, 2018**

Figures 2, 3

Lasophorus zografae Chatzaki 2018: 532, f. 27-28, 31-40 (♂♀); Seyyar et al. 2019: 43, f. 2, 3A-D (♂).

Material examined. 1♂ (IZBA), Azerbaijan: Absheron-Khizi region: Khizi Distr., pitfall traps, V.2025, N.Snegovaya.

Distribution. Greece, Cyprus, Turkey (World Spider Catalog 2026).

Comment. The first record for the fauna of Caucasus.

Zelotes* Gistel, 1848**Zelotes fulvaster* (Simon, 1878)**

Figures 4, 5

For a complete list of twelve taxonomic entries, see World Spider Catalog (2026).

Material examined. 1♂ (IZBA), Azerbaijan: Nakhchivan region: Babek Distr., under a stone, 22.VI.2012, E.Huseynov.

Distribution. France (Corsica), Italy, North Macedonia, Bulgaria, Greece, Turkey, Cyprus, Russia (Europe), Iran (World Spider Catalog 2026).

Comment. The first record for the fauna of Caucasus.

***Zelotes prishutovae* Ponomarev & Tsvetkov, 2006**

Figures 6, 7

Zelotes prishutovae Ponomarev and Tsvetkov, 2006: 13, f. 25-26 (♂♀); Polchaninova et al. 2021: 100, f. 11-12 (♂).

For a complete list of four taxonomic entries, see World Spider Catalog (2026).

Material examined. 1♂ (IZBA), Azerbaijan: Mountainous Shirvan region: Shamakhi Distr., Galebugurd Vill, 19.VI.2025, T.Nuruyeva.

Distribution. Greece, Turkey, Ukraine, Russia (Europe) (World Spider Catalog 2026).

Comment. The first record for the fauna of Caucasus.

Hahniidae Bertkau, 1878

Hahnia C. L. Koch, 1841

Hahnia rossii Brignoli, 1977

Figure 8

Hahnia rossii Brignoli, 1977: 79, f. 46 (♀); Zamani et al. 2020: 581, f. 5A-E, 6A-F (♂♀).

Material examined. 2♀ (IZBA), Azerbaijan: Lankaran-Astara region: Lerik Distr., 38°45'41"E 48°40'28", 1365m, VI.2025, P.Hlaváč; 1♀, Destor env. 38°35'51", VI.2025, P. Hlaváč.

Distribution. Italy, Iran (World Spider Catalog 2026).

Comment. The first record for the fauna of Caucasus.

Pholcidae C. L. Koch, 1850

Artema Walckenaer, 1837

Artema doriae (Thorell, 1881)

Figure 9

Artema doriae Tabrizi, Rad and Hedayati 2014: 35, f. 1M-N, 3L-M (♀).

Artema doriae Aharon, Huber and Gavish-Regev 2017: 30, f. 90-120, 205, 212 (♂♀); Al-Khazali and Najim 2018: 179, pl. 1A-D, 2A-D, 3 (♂♀).

For a complete list of five taxonomic entries, see World Spider Catalog (2026).

Material examined. 1♂ (IZBA), Azerbaijan: Nakhchivan region: Nakhchivan city, on the wall, 21.VIII.2023, N.Sneqovaya

Distribution. Turkey, Israel, United Arab Emirates, Iraq, Iran, and Afghanistan. Introduced to Japan (World Spider Catalog 2026).

Comment. A spider of the genus *Artema* recorded from Nakhchivan (Ordubad district) by Beydizade (2017) was not identified to species level. It likely represent the same species reported here. The first record for the fauna of Caucasus.

Thomisidae Sundevall, 1833***Bassaniodes* Pocock, 1903*****Bassaniodes robustus* (Hahn, 1832)**

Figures 10, 11

For a complete list of thirty-nine taxonomic entries, see World Spider Catalog (2026).

Material examined. 1♂ (IZBA), Azerbaijan: Absheron-Khizi region: Khizi Distr., Yarimca Vill, 15.VI.2022, N.Snegovaya.

Distribution. Europe to Central Asia. In the Caucasus, *Bassaniodes robustus* is reported from Russia (Krasnodar Krai, Stavropol Territory, Dagestan, and North Ossetia), Georgia (Otto 2022).

Comment. The first record for the fauna of Azerbaijan.

Figures 1–9. Copulatory organs. 1. Epigyne of *Berlandina nabozhenkoi* Ponomarev & Tsvetkov, 2006; 2–3. Male palp of *Lasophorus zografae* Chatzaki, 2018; 4–5. Ditto, *Zelotes fulvaster* (Simon, 1878); 6–7. Ditto, *Zelotes prishutovae* Ponomarev & Tsvetkov, 2006; 8. Epigyne of *Hahnia rossii* Brignoli, 1977; 9. Ditto, *Artema doriae* (Thorell, 1881). 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 9. ventral view; 3, 5, 7. retrolateral view. Scale bars = 0.1 mm (8), 0.2 mm (1, 2–7), 0.5 mm (9).

***Synema* Simon, 1864**

***Synema anatolicum* Demir, Aktaş & Topçu, 2009**

Figures 12–16

Synema anatolica Demir, Aktas & Topçu, 2009: 742, f. 1-8 (♂♀).

For a complete list of 5 taxonomic entries, see World Spider Catalog (2026).

Material examined. 1♂ (IZBA), Azerbaijan: Nakhchivan region: Julfa Distr., under stone, 26.VI.2012, E.Huseynov.

Distribution. North Macedonia, Bulgaria, Greece, Turkey, Iran (World Spider Catalog 2026).

Comment. The first record recorded for the fauna of Caucasus.

Trachelidae Simon, 1897

***Cetonana* Strand, 1929**

***Cetonana laticeps* (Canestrini, 1868)**

Figure 17

For a complete list of twenty-three taxonomic entries, see World Spider Catalog (2026).

Material examined. 1♂ (IZBA), Azerbaijan: Guba-Khachmaz: Khachmaz Distr., Nabran vill, pitfall traps, VI.2024, N.Snegovaya.

Distribution. Europe, Turkey, Caucasus (World Spider Catalog 2026). In the Caucasus, this species is reported only from Krasnodar Krai of Russia (Kovblyuk and Ponomarev 2008) and Georgia (Seropian et al. 2023).

Comment. This is the first record of the species for the fauna of Azerbaijan and represents the easternmost known locality of the species.

Discussion

A total of 785 spider species (Arachnida: Aranei) are currently recorded from Azerbaijan, indicating a relatively rich fauna among the South Caucasus countries compared to Armenia (283 species), but fewer than in neighboring Georgia (801 species) (Nentwig et al. 2026). Nevertheless, the spider fauna of Azerbaijan remains understudied and further research is likely to reveal additional species.

Figures 10–17. Copulatory organs. 10–11. Male palp of *Bassanioides robustus* (Hahn, 1832); 12–13. Male and female habitus of *Synema anaticum* Demir, Aktaş & Topçu, 2009; 14–15. Male palp of *Synema anaticum* Demir, Aktaş & Topçu, 2009; 16. Epigyne of *Synema anaticum* Demir, Aktaş & Topçu, 2009; 17. Ditto, *Cetonana laticeps* (Canestrini, 1868). 10, 14, 15, 16, 17 – ventral view; 11 – retrolateral view; 12, 13 – dorsal view. Scale bars = 0.2 mm (10, 11, 14–17), 1 mm (12, 13).

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